

Handling NEGATIVE RESULTS in Diamond Open Access Publishing

A negative or null result occurs when an experiment fails to provide sufficient statistical evidence to support the initial hypothesis.

Often dismissed as failures or less noteworthy, they are frequently left unpublished, creating a bias toward positive findings that undermines the completeness, verifiability and reliability of research.

What can you do as a publisher ?

- ✓ Establish and share policies encouraging and valuing negative results, replication studies, and unexpected findings.
E.g. The University of Liège's open science policy.
- ✓ Encourage early sharing and registering of the study designs and reporting on the negative results.
- ✓ Correct bias towards positive results by paying particular attention to replication studies that fail to reproduce findings.
- ✓ Raise awareness among editorial teams about biases toward positive results.
- ✓ Include all fields. Non-data-driven disciplines, from philosophy to comparative literature and history, can also yield valuable negative findings – such as the absence of expected archival material.

To go further...

DATAACC - Why Are Negative Results Still Six Feet Under?

A report highlighting the significance of reporting negative results and emerging initiatives: <https://www.dataacc.org/en/best-practices/reporting-negative-results/why-are-negative-results-still-six-feet-under/>